

Interaction of Glass Ceiling and Workplace Commitment: Evidence from Banking Industry in Bangladesh

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Abstract

With the noteworthy increase of female employees in the workforce, why do women in top management positions are underrepresented? Does such underrepresentation hamper their commitment toward the organization? As the glass ceiling (GC) is used to label barriers that stop women invisibly from mounting into higher positions, this study concentrates on whether the glass ceiling affects their commitment. This study investigates the relationship between female executives' commitment and the glass ceiling sustained in the organizational structure. A total of 176 female participants were randomly selected from different private banks who completed a structured questionnaire. Results of Cronbach's alpha, KMO, and Bartlett's Test were found acceptable for factor analysis. Management perception and prejudice, corporate policies and practices, general attitudinal problems and stereotyping, and work-life conflict are labeled as GC factors. Results of Pearson Correlation Statistics revealed that the connection between the GC factors and the commitment of female employees is associated negatively, indicating that the presence of glass ceiling hampers their commitment.

Keywords: glass ceiling (gc), corporate policies and practices, attitudinal problems and stereotyping, work-life conflict, commitment, correlation

Introduction

Women account for roughly half of the world's population, making them valuable human capital for countries' socioeconomic growth. Several studies demonstrate that the number of females participating in numerous workplaces has increased across the world throughout the last few decades. According to the ILOSTAT database 2018, the women's participation in the workforce in the USA, EU, South Asia, Australia, and China is almost 66%, 68%, 30%, 72%, and 69%, respectively. However, there remain substantial gender differences in executive leadership positions, and the

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chances for women to progress in higher corporate spots remain scanty. Women in senior roles hold only 24% globally, where nearly half of the workforce are women, and 25% of world businesses have no women in senior management (Catalyst, 2018). Likewise, a thorough study by McKinsey and Company (2018) revealed that women are underrepresented at every level in senior leadership.

What impedes women from career progression into higher ranks has become a significant interest for academics. Scholars found that gender difference in promotion is familiar to many regions and cultures (Al-Manasra, 2013). Furthermore, the workplace has been assumed a career primarily for males (Powell & Graves, 2003), and females are dealing with discrimination, bolted mobility, and biases. Evidently, the glass ceiling affects workforce commitment toward the organization negatively (Dost et al., 2012).

Bangladesh is one of the prominent nations in Southeast Asia, with a GDP growth rate of 7.11% in 2016 and achieving the SDGs 2030 related to poverty, inequality, environmental degradation, prosperity, peace, and justice. Although noticeable achievements in education, health, and empowerment, the female participation ratio is only 35% (ILOSTAT, 2018). According to the Bangladesh Labor Force Survey-2018, women's participation in industry and service is only 16.9% and 23.5%, respectively. The Labor Statistics in Bangladesh-2018, BBS, found women heavily participate in skilled agricultural, forestry, fisheries, which seldom ensure women's career progression into senior management positions.

Universally, gender differences in various professions have become a common concern of the research. In Bangladesh, gender inequality issues have been received attention over the last decade. However, most of the study has mainly focused on socioeconomic matters like poverty, illiteracy, and violence. Some studies, directly or indirectly related to the glass ceiling, are conducted by Zafarullah (2000), Afza and Newaz (2008), Kamal and Sabrin (2014), Shirage et al. (2018), and Mollah and Uddin (2018). However, the effect of the glass ceiling on commitment has not been substantially researched yet. This study continues with this notion and contributes to the study of the glass ceiling effects on commitment.

Objectives of the study

Based on the above background, the objectives of this study are

- a) to find out the GC factors impeding women career progression into higher management positions in the banking sector; and
- b) to analyze the association of the glass ceiling on women's commitment towards organizations

Review of literature

Glass ceiling

The term glass ceiling is a metaphorical expression consisting of two separate words, *Glass* and *Ceiling*. As said by Hymowitz and Schell Hardt (1986), these two words

stand for a set of unseen, real, or perceived obstacles that hinder women's advancement opportunities. They published an article in the extensively read Wall Street Journal where they used, for the first time, the glass ceiling metaphor as an impenetrable obstacle between females and executive suits. According to Oakley (2000), what causes the glass ceiling can be separated into two types: work-family conflict and communicative system, and social and cultural issues like stereotypes and leadership patterns.

A study conducted by Afza and Newaz (2008) identifies the features deciding the glass ceiling's existence and affecting women's career progression in Bangladesh. Those studies found that management perception and work environment play the most significant role in creating a glass ceiling phenomenon. Again, Women career progression is positively impacted by the factors like concern about children at home, level of appreciation from the co-workers in the workplace, the extreme length of the working hours in the job, the intention of the male employees to grip the higher and influential positions, negative conception regarding the competitiveness of the women at work (Shirage et al., 2018).

Organizational commitment

The commitment was termed as an eagerness in continuing the progression of activity and reluctance to change plans, often due to a sense of responsibility to stay the course (Vance, 2006). Organizational commitment pertains to an employee's identity, emotional attachment, and a strong desire to sustain the organization (Khuong & Chi, 2017). A highly committed employee is deemed to be spontaneously eager to run the extra mile for the firm, keep a connection with it and its goals and philosophy (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Thus, organizational commitment can be considered a significant factor in differentiating tremendously functional organizations from less effective ones.

Several cross-cultural types of research have been conducted revolving around gender influence in organizational commitment (Voloshin, 2016). The insight of the glass ceiling may influence employee performance, such as commitment. The study of Downes et al. (2014) showed that the perceived glass ceiling positively influenced commitment. According to Foley (1998), there is a negative relationship between the perceived glass ceiling and significant work results, such as growth expectations, commitment, satisfaction, and intention to quit the organization. Saleem et al. (2017) reported that the glass ceiling harmed women's output and could halt their organizational success role.

Glass ceiling and commitment

Discrimination may result in amplified work strain and decreased job fulfillment and commitment (Sanchez & Brock, 1996). Employees' commitment towards the organization tends to suffer a lot when alteration appears in wages, promotion, and

recognition. Gutek et al. (1996) said that when female employees experience perceived discrimination in their workplaces, they feel the reduced controls and absence of respect and exhibit lower commitment.

Like discriminatory issues, the glass ceiling also has a salient impact on commitment. A modest level of association between the glass ceiling and commitment has been found by Dost et al. (2012). According to their suggestion, corporate policies should be designed and developed to minimize glass ceiling practices. When a work environment is hugely reigned by gender biases, female employees working in that environment tend to decrease organizational commitment (Rosin & Korabik, 1991). Also, gender biases hurt female employees' commitment toward their organization (Imam & Shah, 2013). Thus, to assure employee commitment, the organizations should delete or reduce the glass ceiling.

Methods

Participants

The study population was the entry and mid-level female executives working in private banks in Bangladesh. As the exact figure of the population is unknown, Cochran's (1977) method was used to fix the sample size, $n=176$, assuming the confidence level of 95% for z value of 1.96, $p=.50$, and margin of error, $.075$. And a random sampling method was used to choose the participants.

Measures

A structured questionnaire developed by Afza and Newaz (2008) was used to measure GC factors. An 18-item commitment scale developed by Allen and Meyer (1996) was used to measure the commitment. Before finalizing the questionnaire, the subject matter expert's opinion was received, and a pilot survey was conducted. Questions were constructed employing a five-point Likert scale ranging from 5 (*strongly agree*) to 1 (*strongly disagree*). A total of 260 questionnaires were distributed. Finally, after avoiding incomplete data, 176 valid questionnaires were used for the study. The survey response rate was about 74%, where the paper-based survey questionnaire method, including enumerators' scheduling and the online survey, accounts for 77.62% and 38%, respectively.

Test of Internal-Consistency and Data Adequacy

Cronbach's α , for GC and commitment scales were found 0.701 and 0.729, respectively, which are acceptable and adequate, according to Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994. The KMO (Kaiser Meyer Olkin) score was 0.638 and .732 for glass ceiling and commitment scales (Table 1), respectively, indicating the sample was adequate and acceptable for factor analysis, according to George & Mallery (2011). Bartlett's test of Sphericity for all scales found a statistically significant value, $p < 0.001$, i.e., the correlation matrix is not an identity matrix.

Table 1*KMO and Bartlett's Test*

	GC Scale	Commitment Scale
KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy	.631	.732
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
Approx. Chi-Square	483.728	1.233E3
Df	105	189
Sig.	.000	.000

Note. Compiled by Author.

Results and Discussion

Respondents' sociodemographic profile

The study results revealed demographic and socioeconomic information for female employees working in different private banks in the table below.

Table 2*Respondents' Sociodemographic Profile*

Variables	<i>n</i> =176	%	Variables	<i>n</i> =176	%
Respondents' Age			Education		
Below 25 Years	21	11.9	Bachelor	67	38.1
25 to 35 Years	83	47.1	Master's	100	56.8
36 to 45 Years	65	36.9	Ph.D. and Others	9	5.1
46 and above	7	3.9			
Marital Status			Job Position		
Unmarried	54	30.6	Executive level	90	40.1
Married	119	67.7	Mid-level	86	50.1
Widowed	3	1.7	Management		
No. of Children			No. of Dependents		
No Children	24	12.5	No dependent	112	63.6
Have Children	98	71.6	Have dependent	64	36.4
Experience			No. of Promotions in Career		
Below 5 years	105	58.6	None	71	40.5
5 to 10 years	60	34.1	One	62	35.2
11 to 15 years	9	6.2	Two	23	13.0
Above 15 years	2	1.1	More than Two	9	5.1

Note. Compiled by author

Exploratory Statistics of Survey Variables

Through PCA, four components explained more than 10% variance individually (Table 3). These components have eigenvalues well above one and explained 55.709% of the total variances, acceptable for factor analysis, suggesting fair values (Peterson, 1994).

Table 3

Total Variance Explained (GC Scale)

Component	Initial Eigenvalues		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.629	18.781	18.781
2	2.016	14.401	33.182
3	1.734	12.384	45.566
4	1.420	10.143	55.709

Note. Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The pattern matrix table (Table 4) shows the weighing of items in each factor, the correlation between the variables and the factors, and finally shows the labeling of the extracted factors. Here, variables having communalities < .40 and correlation coefficients < 0.50 were dropped.

Table 4

Pattern Matrix^a, Factor Labeling, and Communalities (GC Scale)

PCA Item	Factor loading				Communalities
	1	2	3	4	
Factor I: Management Perception and Prejudice					
Q8	.833				.690
Q7	.830				.544
Q6	.641				.663
Factor II: Corporate Policies and Practices					
Q12		.777			.620
Q10		.738			.577
Q14		.564			.576
Q13		.538			.428

Factor III: General Attitudinal Problems & Stereotyping		
Q1	.777	.482
Q3	.738	.581
Q4	.564	.518
Q2	.538	.418
Factor IV: Work-Life Conflict		
Q11	.834	.515
Q9	.686	.520
Q5	.409	.665

Note. Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

^a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

Factor I: Management Prejudice and Perception

The above analysis advocates that management prejudice and perception is enormously liable for women's career progression. This factor accounts for 18.781% of the total variance and explained three variables, Q8, Q7, and Q6. These findings correspond with the conclusions of Crampton and Mishra (1999), Afza and Newaz (2008), Jogulu and Wood (2011), and Lucifora and Vigani (2016).

Factor II: Corporate Policy and Practices

Corporate Policy and Practices accounts for 14.401% of the total variance and comprises four variables, Q12, Q13, Q14, and Q10. Studies of Sinclair (2000), Tharenou (1999), Afza and Newaz (2008), and Rezina and Mahmood (2016) and analysis results indicate that organizational policies and practices create barriers for women in career progression.

Factor III: General Attitudinal Problems & Stereotyping

This factor explained four variables, Q1, Q2, Q, and Q4, accounted for 12.38% of the total variance. Some psychological attributes often stop them from prospering in career. The findings of Pillai et al. (2011), and Mollah and Uddin (2018), Bombuwela and Alwis (2013), Kamal and Sabrin (2014), Rezina and Mahmood (2016), and Lucifora and Vigani (2016) also depicted similar results.

Factor IV: Work-Life Conflict

The analysis also found that women's concern for family ranks first in most cases, which often impedes career progression. This factor comprises three variables, Q5, Q 11, and Q9, and accounts for 10.143% of the total variance. The study of Lyness and Heilman (2006), Afza and Newaz (2008), Appelbaum et al. (2012), Pillai et al. (2011), Bombuwela and Alwis (2013), and Kamal and Sabrin (2014) explored similar findings.

Table 5*Descriptive Statistics and Reliability Test of GC Factors*

Factors	I	II	III	IV
Mean	4.7159	6.8182	6.0227	5.2670
Std. Deviation (SD)	1.80060	.94307	1.18943	1.69756
Items	3	4	4	3
Cronbach's α	.804	.796	.764	.737

Note. Compiled by Author.

After labeling the factors, descriptive statistics and reliability test was conducted (Table 5). It can be inferred that management perception and prejudice is the most significant GC factors. The PCA extraction method was also used to original variables of Allen and Meyer's 18-item commitment scale (1990). Table 6 presents only the significant factor loadings for the three factors, which explained almost 56.581% of the total variances. The 1st factor explained 28.259% of the total variance, whereas the 2nd and 3rd factors account for 16.436% and 11.885% of the total variance explained, respectively.

Table 6*Total Variance Explained (Commitment Scale)*

Component	Initial Eigenvalues		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
C1	4.239	28.259	28.259
C2	2.465	16.436	44.696
C3	1.783	11.885	56.581

Note. Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

It can be seen that the six items for affective commitment converged strictly in factor 1 (Table 7). For continuance commitment, all items, except the 7th item, merged under factor 2. Likewise, for normative commitment, items, except items 13 and 14, converged under factor 3. Hence, items 7,13, and 14 were dropped since they did not load onto relevant factors. Again, none of the items of any scale did converge onto other factors.

Table 7*Rotated Component Matrix^a (Commitment Scale)*

PCA Items	Factor Loading			Communalities
	1	2	3	
Affective Commitment				
C6	.800			.663
C2	.770			.612
C4	.766			.604
C1	.756			.591
C3	.685			.480
C5	.625			.407
Continuance Commitment				
C9		.826		.691
C10		.744		.637
C8		.690		.481
C11		.646		.455
C12		.632		.439
Normative Commitment				
C18			.787	.680
C17			.783	.631
C15			.766	.625
C16			.673	.490

Note. Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

^a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

After dropping those items, α for the new scale was found .814. Again, every three scales' reliability in the following table (Table 8) shows that any items might not be considered for deletion as Cronbach's Alpha values of items deleted are smaller in all scales. Hence, the items for affective, continuance, and normative commitment are

stable, except for some items for continuance and normative scale, and are unique, i.e., the Allen and Meyer's organizational commitment scale was appropriate.

Table 8*Reliability Statistics (New Scales)*

Commitment Scale	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted					
			1	2	3	4	5	6
Affective	6	.814	.761	.773	.799	.798	.806	.759
Continuance	5	.766	*	.751	.700	.681	.725	.755
Normative	4	.768	*	*	.691	.751	.732	.673

Note: Compiled by Author; * Dropped Items 7, 13, and 14.

It is apparent from the results, GC factors like management perception and prejudice, corporate policies and practices, general attitudinal problems and stereotyping, and work-life conflict influence women's career progression, affecting their organizational commitment (Table 9).

Table 9*Correlation between GC factors and Organizational Commitment*

	<i>n</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. AC	176	-						
2. CC	176	.214**	-					
3. NC	176	.235**	.296**	-				
4. MPP	176	-.179*	-.004	-.035	-			
5. WLC	176	-.112	.060	-.091	.046	-		
6. GAPS	176	-.112	-.040	-.068	.182*	.034	-	
7. CPP	176	.035	-.058	-.098	-.041	.108	.047	-

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; AC= Affective Commitment, CC= Continuance Commitment, NC= Normative Commitment, MPP= Management Perception and Prejudice, WLC= Work-Life Conflict, GAPS= General Attitudinal Problems and Stereotyping, CPP= Corporate Policies and Practices.

The above results also reveal that management perception is negatively related to all kinds of commitment. Therefore, the perceived glass ceiling in management perception lowers organizational commitment (Khuong & Chi, 2017). Work-life conflict is also negatively correlated to the affective and normative commitment and has a low correlation with continuance commitment. And this finding is consistent with Oreyzi Samani et al. (2009) and Pirhayat et al. (2012). Then general attitudinal

problems and stereotyping is also negatively related to all kinds of commitment. The findings of Ragins and Winkel (2011) are similar to the results. Finally, corporate policies and practices is negatively related to continuance commitment, normative commitment, and a low degree of correlation with affective commitment (ILO, 2002, & Rosener, 1990). Dost et al. (2012) found that the glass ceiling negatively affects employees' commitment. Heilman & Okimoto (2007) concluded that the more female employees experienced gender discrimination, the less affective commitment they had, and the stronger was their intention to quit their jobs.

Therefore, organizations ought to understand the advantages of breaking the glass ceiling and innovating a biased and discrimination-free atmosphere by improving their corporate culture. Also, women should be more conscious of their strengths to develop and weaknesses to repair to unlock their ability and achieve their objectives.

As the glass ceiling is still unfamiliar with business management in Bangladesh, future researchers may explore the same subject, with a larger sample size and more complete questionnaires focusing on other sectors. Furthermore, researchers should get more appropriate respondents to engage in their study because many declined to participate during this investigation when approached.

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